

Observe to Sustain – How to Enable Beyond 5G Networks to Target Sustainability Goals

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Abstract—The emergence of 5G systems and beyond, along with state-of-the-art cloud and software engineering solutions, have brought to a radical shift of networking technologies with respect to the previous generations. However, the increased performance and flexibility have come at the cost of reduced sustainability, not only from an environmental standpoint but, in turn, affecting economic and societal sustainability as well. Infrastructure owners can introduce power management solutions in their datacenters, but the improvement is negligible unless tenant operating on top of the physical infrastructure are enabled and incentivized to customize their slices and their applications towards more energy efficient and carbon neutral profiles. For these reasons, the 6Green project has designed an Observability framework for estimating the energy consumption and the carbon footprint of an entire network slice, or of edge-computing applications attached to it. This paper highlights the rationale behind the 6Green approach and provides a high-level description of the observability framework.

Keywords—6G, Observability, Sustainability, Energy Efficiency

I. INTRODUCTION

In the last years, 5G systems and beyond have been radically shifting the technological and architectural foundations of networks by enabling the complete integration with heterogeneous challenging applications through a full-stack programmability. To this end, state-of-the-art cloud and software engineering solutions have been widely embraced and extended for decoupling network services from infrastructure hardware, and dividing them into a number of different elementary software modules, called microservices or network functions. Through the proper composition of these elementary software modules, 5G network slices can be realized in as-a-Services fashion to host multiple applications (and their tenants) while coping with their custom requirements.

If on one side, this approach has led to a radically new technological framework offering multi-tenant flexibility well beyond classical software-defined environments; on the other side, it posed more than a concern on environmental sustainability.

First studies on deployed infrastructures [1]-[4] outlined a tangible increase on the overall power consumption, quite far from the levels of energy efficiency targeted during the 5G design. This “aggregated” effect obviously depends on a

complex mix of different causes at different levels of the architecture, which can be hardly summarized in a simplified fashion.

Moreover, it can be highlighted that the optimization of energy consumption cannot easily be adopted as a potential target in management operations of 5G networks. This is because energy consumption is currently a performance index only at the infrastructure level, and it is not propagated to the 5G platform and to its slices.

While infrastructure owners can adopt sophisticated power management schemes to reduce power consumption and carbon footprint of their datacenters, it is not possible to act and to propagate back this information to the upper layers. In detail, no feedback is provided to vertical stakeholders to inform them about the energy consumption caused by their running applications and slices, and to promote greener and more sustainable profiles in performance requirements and workload generation. In other words, the current 5G system is hindering the vertical integration of environmental sustainability solutions, and it does not allow its tenants to customize their slices and their applications towards more energy efficient and carbon neutral profiles.

Starting from this context, the 6Green project [5] is actively extending the 5G architectural framework by designing a complete observability framework able (i) to retrieve energy consumption of hardware infrastructures; (ii) to break down the different contributions from any software instance/ microservice in the 5G infrastructure; as well as (iii) to recombine these contributions to estimate the consumption levels ascribable to the virtual resources and artefacts consumed by upper-level 5G stakeholders.

For example, the 6Green Observability framework is specifically designed to estimate the energy consumption and the carbon footprint of an entire network slice, or of edge-computing applications attached to it. This paper highlights the rationale behind the 6Green approach and provides a high-level description of the observability framework. Preliminary results are provided to give an idea of the level of accuracy that can be achieved.

The remaining of this paper is organized as follows. Section II introduces the 6Green project and its main concepts, with Section III focusing on how the presence of multiple stakeholders is handled, and Section IV on the observability

Fig. 1. The 6Green SBA.

framework. Preliminary results are presented in Section V, and conclusions are drawn in Section VI.

II. 6GREEN APPROACH

The 6Green Project has been conceived to design and realize an innovative service-based and holistic ecosystem characterized by a high level of flexibility, scalability and sustainability to foster the carbon footprint reduction of 5/6G networks and vertical applications by a factor of 10 or more. The 6Green SBA, as depicted in Fig. 1, is composed of:

- an enhanced observability, monitoring, and analytics framework to support control/management/external information flows that can be relevant to drive sustainable network operations,
- a new AI-driven decision and operations framework, hosting pluggable in-network actuation intelligence for triggering the management and control planes in a fully integrated fashion,
- the support of enhanced control policies to flexibly assist SBA agile and elastic adaptations,
- the full integration of management plane functions and their extension to support fast and efficient operations
- the integration of the management of edge-cloud resources to be dedicated to the vertical applications, to enable a full coordination between the 5/6G network and the application domains.

6Green aims to do so by leveraging on the most promising technological enablers, such as novel paradigms, protocols and technologies for the optimal exploitation of power management across the 6G edge-cloud continuum, along with sustainable AI/ML, observability and zero-touch automation.

In the project conception, the evolution of the 5G Service-Based Architecture (SBA) towards 6G passes through three main ground-breaking innovations, that will permit, on the one side, the smooth and rapid reconfiguration of the ecosystem towards more energy- and carbon-efficient configurations and, on the other side, assess the indirect energy/carbon footprint induced by any stakeholder on the infrastructure, consequently allowing more responsible and sustainable practices. Such ground-breaking innovations, representing the foundation of the 6Green vision, are described in the following subsections.

A. Edge Agility

Edge Agility is a paradigm that aims to transition from the traditional “Cloud Agility” approach to a new concept of dynamically moving applications and services within the edge-cloud continuum. In this new paradigm, vertical applications and network services will be deployed and horizontally scaled according to user or infrastructure-driven events, allowing seamless relocation across different geographical areas. This will be achieved by introducing novel features at the service mesh sidecars [6], including the ability to scale Network Functions (NFs) and Vertical Applications (vApps) to zero when not in use, and providing mechanisms for proactive and reactive relocation operations based on policies.

Control plane integration will also allow to opportunistically move the latency budget between connectivity (in terms of PDU session or distance from the edge) and computing (the time taken by software processes composing network functions or application components), while management operations will be conducted to quickly scale to zero the footprint of slices and vertical applications in unused areas of the continuum, while efficiently resuming operation when needed.

B. Green Elasticity

Green Elasticity is a paradigm that aims to dynamically and adaptively provide energy-aware hardware-assisted acceleration to network functions and vertical applications to enable smart vertical scalability across the three domains of 5/6G environments: from the vertical domain, through the network (slice), down to the infrastructure. It involves extending cloud-native service mesh technologies with new capabilities to dynamically transfer critical tasks between software and hardware accelerators. Automated decision engines will be developed to manage and trade off various types of compute and network resources, with the goal of meeting service requirements while reducing overall energy consumption.

Hardware acceleration, such as programmable hardware and GPUs or FPGAs, can significantly lower processing latency with respect to pure software artefacts, and can be applied for network tasks and business logic. However, its

efficacy strictly depends on the workload volume offloaded from the software level: hardware acceleration engines usually exhibit low power-consumption dependency against their usage, and significant energy savings can only be achieved by putting the engines into standby low power modes. Therefore, hardware acceleration becomes energetically/environmentally advantageous against to pure software processing when applied to large volume of the time-varying workloads, or when the speeding up one element in the NF/vApp component chain can bring to optimal end-to-end configurations/deployments.

Thus, Green Elasticity is a crucial mean for dynamically distributing the time-varying, end-to-end latency budgets of vertical applications across the domains, while holistically optimizing the trade-off between the energy/carbon footprint and the performance of network and application artefacts. Through this paradigm, elasticity operations will be no longer constrained to a single domain, but they will rather propagate to the other domains, allowing to jointly adapt/consolidate the service meshes of vertical applications and network slices to optimally exploit the available computing/networking resources.

C. Energy-Aware Backpressure

The Energy-aware Backpressure consists in a set of cross-domain observability mechanisms and analytics to evaluate the energy and the carbon footprint that a vertical application, a slice, or the overall 5/6G network is inducing onto the edge-cloud infrastructure. The infrastructure consumes energy in accordance with the aggregation of workloads of the hosted artefacts (i.e., network function and application components); while in current cloud environments power consumption information is usually consumed only within the infrastructure, 6Green aims to process, infer, and expose this information at both the 5/6G SBA and vertical application levels, including their network slices.

Hardware-level energy consumption metrics will be collected and divided/mapped onto each hosted tenant through adaptive AI-driven analytics. The SBA will be accordingly extended to acquire these energy consumption metrics, and to further classify and expose them to the accountable vertical.

The cross-domain observability will be complemented by a set of business models to showcase the mutual benefits related to a win-win approach based on the optimization of energy consumption and carbon footprint to all members of the ecosystem. Economic incentives will be defined and provided to motivate upper stakeholders to acquire and use resources as-a-Service, which would improve energy-savings/OpEx reductions for the underlying stakeholders.

III. A MULTI-STAKEHOLDER ECOSYSTEM

As introduced in the previous section, the concept of energy-aware backpressure has been defined in 6Green to represent the joint involvement of all the stakeholders in the propagation of information related to the energy and resources consumption ascribable to a vertical application, a slice, or the SBA.

This involvement, as shown in Fig. 2, is heavily domain-specific: on the one hand, each stakeholder delivers the information of interest for the other players in the ecosystem, on the other hand such information is delivered in a format that is relevant to the specific recipient and fulfils isolation and privacy requirements. For instance, while an infrastructure

Fig. 2. Information flow among the involved domains for supporting energy-aware backpressure.

provider may be prone to disclose the level of computational resources consumed by a specific slice, it may decline to divulge the geographical location of the hosting datacenter. In the same way, a vertical may be interested in the economic benefits coming from the usage of renewable resources without taking an interest in their maintenance costs.

The operations performed by each domain can be summarized as follows:

1. Infrastructure: measurement of the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), that are, energy consumption and resource usage of the single virtualized components (i.e., containers or pods) which may be a network function or an application component.
2. Network platform: map the aforementioned KPIs to the correct network functions, slices, applications components through appropriate analytics that combine such KPIs with traditional 5G network KPIs (e.g., number and type of active PDU sessions, UE density, UE handover rate, etc.).
3. Vertical: algorithms, policies, and run-time optimization mechanisms, fed by the received KPIs paired with green business models, to drive Day-0, 1 and 2 lifecycle operations with the aim of reducing the energy consumption ascribable to the vertical application.

It is worth noting that, according to the specifications emerging from the preliminary design of 6G technologies, a potential extension of 6Green will foresee the inclusion of end-users as one of the full-fledged stakeholders involved in the 6G ecosystem. In order to convey information in a comprehensible way for every human being, Key Value Indicators (KVIs) will play a crucial role, along with a scoring system for evaluating the overall energy/carbon consumed/emitted indirectly by the end-user, as well as the fairness, security and accessibility achieved by the underlying 6G telecom platform. A first approach could be the utilization of the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) [7] as a starting point for the definition of the KVIs.

In this paper, we are concentrating our attention on the mechanisms and analytics required for inferring the amount of energy and resources ascribable to a virtualized component, which also entails the attribution of the “embodied energy consumption”: the energy devoted to the execution of all the processes needed to have the bare-metal server and the virtualized environments (i.e., a container management platform) work. It is not trivial to map the embodied energy consumption to containers/pods because hardware resources are not reserved for single pods. The next section will show how to extend infrastructure-layer observability to perform the mapping, leveraging container/pod profiling and additional information regarding resource (i.e., not only CPU, but also networking and memory) consumption.

IV. THE OBSERVABILITY FRAMEWORK

The observability framework represents one of the main achievements of 6Green and is a crucial tool to promote the sustainability of the ecosystem. Its importance is twofold: on the one hand, it provides the data needed to inform all the stakeholders on their footprint and to feed the AI-based algorithms taking control and management decisions on the network; on the other hand, it represents the first link¹ between the physical and the virtualized domains that is so important for the creation of a homogeneous ecosystem that promotes the interaction among stakeholders.

In this respect, the framework is composed of three main modules: the Infrastructure Data Analytics Function (IDAF) belongs to the Infrastructure domain and is meant to collect, elaborate and expose energy and performance metrics of the bare-metal resources towards the 6G SBA. At the Network Platform domain, two 5G SBA functions, namely the Management Data Analytics Function (MDAF) and the Network Data Analytics Function (NWDAF), have been extended for being included in the framework. Their extension covers the “green” side of the metrics collection and analysis, spanning from the collection of energy- and carbon-metrics coming from the infrastructure to their breakdown on a per-slice/vApp basis.

A. The Infrastructure Data Analytics Function (IDAF)

The green block in Fig. 3 represents the Infrastructure Data Analytics Function (IDAF) which is responsible for exposing infrastructure related metrics.

Since the Network Platform and the Infrastructure Provider are usually owned by different stakeholders, it is essential to collect the data in the two domains separately: this reasoning leads to the separation between IDAF and MDAF. As a result, the MDAF does not have direct access to the infrastructure, but only to the metrics exposed by the IDAF.

As shown in Fig. 3, the IDAF includes five components exposing metrics in a Prometheus-like format. cAdvisor and Kube State Metrics (KSM) expose information regarding the Kubernetes cluster. The former is embedded in kubelet (i.e., the main K8s agent responsible for managing the deployment of pods and for the health of the K8s cluster) and exposes the utilization of the computing resource (e.g., CPU, memory, networking, etc.) per container. The latter is an additional service that exposes the state of K8s objects (e.g., pods, nodes, replicaset, statefulset, etc.).

NodeExporter and Scaphandre [8] expose metrics of the bare-metal servers. The former exposes a wide variety of hardware- and kernel-related metrics among which it worth mentioning the resource (e.g., CPU, memory, networking, etc.) utilization of the servers. The latter exposes the power consumption of every single process (including containers and VMs) running on the server. Scaphandre relies on the Intel Running Average Power Limit (RAPL) [9] counters and on the time spent on each process by the CPU to compute the power consumption per process. So far, the power consumption exposed by Scaphandre includes only the CPU and, only in some cases, the DRAM controller consumption. Therefore, being the CPU the most power-hungry component of servers, the metrics should be somewhat reliable for processes not needing GPUs.

Finally, the Raritan exporter is in charge of exposing the power consumption of the Raritan Power Distribution Units (PDUs). In detail, we used the IX7™ PDU Controller by Raritan.

Fig. 3. Internal architecture of the observability framework.

¹ The second link is represented by the actuation of the decisions coming from the AI to be applied on the infrastructure and is out of the scope of this paper.

The aforementioned metrics are saved on a Prometheus database that is accessible for to all the three functions (i.e., IDAF, MDAF, NWDAF). Prometheus is a time series database collecting metrics composed of a timestamp, a value and optionally key-value labels.

B. The Management Data Analytics Function (MDAF)

The MDAF has been defined in 3GPP TS 28.533 [10], to retrieve Operations, Administration and Maintenance (OAM) data and to perform analytics, as well as provide predictions, on a per-NF or per-slice basis. Since the current definition already contemplates predicting resource usage according to the load level or resource utilization associated with the SBA NFs, its evolution in 6Green has extended the plethora of collected data to the energy context and introduced the interaction with the IDAF. By combining metrics coming from both the infrastructure and the management, the MDAF allows to estimate the current and the future carbon/energy footprint induced to the computing and offloading resources in the edge-cloud continuum, and even the availability and the use of green energy sources and hardware offloading engines.

As shown in Fig. 3, the MDAF is essentially composed of three blocks: the metric collector, the analytics blocks (which may be more than one) and the exporter.

The *metric collector* exploits the prometheus-api-client library to interrogate the Prometheus instance for retrieving Scaphandre and cAdvisor metrics, therefore, the main goal is to acquire the power consumption of each process and the resource utilization of each container. It also has the ability to identify the metrics that do not belong to virtualized components, that is, all those kernel processes that are needed in order for the server and everything on top (hypervisor and the container orchestration platforms) to work correctly. We assume that the servers would be off if not for the virtualized components (e.g., there may be a containerized 5G network running on K8s); hence the total power consumption of these processes represents the so-called embodied power consumption.

The *analytics* blocks are a set of pluggable algorithms devoted to data manipulation, such as the computation of the embodied power consumption of the virtualized components, the “metric enrichment” to cope with Scaphandre inability of acquiring container labels for their univocal identification, and, of course, the actual mapping of the kernel-level power metrics coming from the IDAF.

Finally, the *exporter* goal is to expose the metrics in a Prometheus-like format the newly generated metrics. It leverages once again on the prometheus-api-client library to respect the Prometheus format.

C. The Network Data Analytics Function (NWDAF)

While the implementation of the MDAF has been minimally explored so far in the literature [11], the NWDAF on the other hand is collecting more interest [12], [13], likely due to its association with the ETSI ENI specification [14]. The NWDAF is conceived to acquire monitored data at the edge and the cloud part of the infrastructure and to produce and analyze added-value KPIs, like forecasts of NF workloads, etc. Data collection is performed by subscription to events provided by network functions.

The evolution of the NWDAF in 6Green, in line with what anticipated for the MDAF, deals with the acquisition of control-plane data and their elaboration along the

Table 1. Mean value and standard deviation of the difference in % between the MDAF and the Scaphandre container power consumption.

container	mean value	std
iperf server	15.98 %	4.81
iperf client	16.64 %	4.16

management ones coming from the MDAF into KPIs able to characterize the energy-efficiency level of the current SBA deployment and make forecasts accordingly. A prototype of the NWDAF NF has already been presented in [15] with a modular, microservice-based structure composed of a metric collector, a storage and a pluggable analytics module.

V. PRELIMINARY RESULTS

5G NFs should be deployed as Virtual Machines (VMs) or containers. In this section we focus on containers that, being lightweight and more flexible, are the envisioned implementation for 6G NFs.

Herein, we present preliminary results concerning the power consumption mapping performed by the MDAF. First, the system setup is introduced in detail; then, results compared to state-of-the-art solutions are presented.

A. System Setup

One of the most well-known container management platforms (i.e., Kubernetes (K8s) [16]) is used. In further detail, a 2-node K8s cluster is installed on two Intel servers. The former server has 4 CPUs, 264 Gb of RAM and a Mellanox MT27500 NIC; while the latter has 2 CPUs, 96 Gb of RAM and the same NIC.

Regarding the K8s cluster, the more powerful one hosts the master node and the other one the worker; both nodes are able to run containerized workloads since the master was untainted. In addition, most of the monitoring tools (i.e., KSM, Raritan exporter cAdvisor, Prometheus and the MDAF) are installed only once in the more powerful server, while the remaining (i.e., Node Exporter and Scaphandre) are installed in both servers. Most of the aforementioned monitoring tools, MDAF included, are deployed in the form of docker containers for convenience purposes.

In order to perform tests, we rely on a well-known network testing tool: iperf [17]. One couple of iperf server and client are deployed as K8s containers: one in each K8s node in order to generate inter-node traffic. Moreover, TCP traffic is selected. We run the test for one hour, and after the test we retrieve data from the Prometheus database which has a 10 second scrape interval. In the following subsection results concerning power consumption are presented.

B. Evaluation

As mentioned before, results will focus on power consumption. Figs. 4 and 5 show the power consumption of the servers and of the iperf containers retrieved from different sources. The blue plot represents the power consumption of the whole server (i.e., including every component) measured by the Raritan power outlet. The yellow plot represents the power consumption of the whole server measured by Intel RAPL. The orange plot shows the power consumption of the iperf containers (i.e., the server and the client in Figs. 4 and 5 respectively); finally, the gray plot represents the power consumption of the iperf containers produced by the MDAF.

Fig. 4. Power consumption of the server hosting the K8s master node (blue and yellow) and of the iperf server container (orange and grey).

Fig. 5. Power consumption of the server hosting the K8s worker node (blue and yellow) and of the iperf client container (orange and grey).

First, let us focus on the server-level results: in both figures the Raritan power consumption is higher (around double) than the RAPL one; this is to be expected since the RAPL component only measures the power consumption of the CPU, while the Raritan one takes into account every component including the power supply. Then, considering also the gray and orange plots, it is worth noticing that, as expected, the container power consumption plots have lower values with respect to the other two. Moreover, the difference between the container and the server plots is almost constant for the whole duration of the test even at 11:40 when the iperf bandwidth is halved; this highlights that our solution (the MDAF) misses a fixed value which corresponds to the server components other than the CPU.

Additionally, a comparison between the proposed MDAF and the state-of-the-art solution Scaphandre is needed. In both Figs. 4 and 5 we can notice that Scaphandre underestimates the container power consumption since it considers only the container direct usage of the CPU. While our proposed MDAF takes into account the indirect power consumption due to all the kernel processes needed to keep the whole system (virtualization platforms included) up and running. Finally, in Table 1, the mean value and standard deviation of the difference in percentage between the MDAF and the Scaphandre container power consumption are reported. For both the server and client the mean value is around 16% with low standard deviation, therefore the added value of the MDAF could be a fixed (depending on the application) value that could be calculated rather than measured.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The improvements in performance and offered services boosted by 5G systems and beyond have taken a toll on the

environmental, economic and societal sustainability of ICT technology. For this reason, the 6Green project is developing solutions able to involve all the stakeholders in the 5/6G ecosystem towards joint sustainable goals by designing an ecosystem able to retrieve and spread information on the energy consumed at hardware level and motivate the stakeholders relying on the infrastructure to adopt more virtuous behaviors through incentives.

In this respect, it is crucial to break down the different contributions from any software instance/ microservice in the 5G infrastructure and recombine them to estimate the consumption levels ascribable to the virtual resources and artefacts consumed by upper-level stakeholders. The proposed Observability framework fulfils this goal by providing a multi-domain system able to retrieve energy and resource consumption from the Infrastructure domain, and expose it to the Network Platform domain for further identifying the overhead ascribable to any virtual instances running on the hardware.

In particular, results show that the proposed extended MDAF is able to break down even the embodied footprint among containers, which can play a key role in spreading awareness on sustainability among verticals.

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